

THE CONCEPT OF “HEART” IN THE LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE

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Annotation. It is thought of as the comparable and characteristics of idea heart in the language image of world what's more, the language units are separated into the accompanying lexical-semantic gatherings, for example, "dread", pity, feeling, love, temperament, graciousness in Uzbek and English languages. The language units of these languages have a similar significance; likewise Uzbek and English languages units are viewed as the utilizations of these languages.

Keywords: lexical-semantic groups, idioms, phraseological words, language picture of world.

Introduction. Idea can be named as a theoretical thought, a psychological image, a unit of thought, related with a comparing portrayal in language, that indicates every one of the items in a given class or class of elements, connections, peculiarities, or connections between them, framed by intellectually consolidating some or every one of the qualities of a substantial or conceptual, genuine or fanciful item. Ideas exist in the psyche as unique elements free of terms used to communicate them. The significant substance of the key ideas decide public idea circle, that illustrates, watches, public social legacy. [1]

Through singling out the idea circle and characterizing the semantic means expressing ideas we can uncover impossible to miss public and social values apparent by this ethnos. Idea heart is affirmed the presence and a specific connection between these ideas in a etymological societies. The exploration of idea heart, as pictures of culture, shaping the premise of the Uzbek and English public image of the world and is one of the central social ideas, assists with recognizing the ethnic idiosyncrasies of reasoning and profound existence of these individuals. Today the hypothesis and practice of worldwide correspondence draw in an ever increasing number of researchers, as it has

¹ E. Vereschagina, V.G. Kostamarov, Looking for new ways to develop linguo country studies: concept speech behavioral tactics. Moscow, 1999, pp. 84-86

become clear that the assessment of their concerns requires aptitude from the unique areas of study. It's notable that misconception can annihilate the connection between individuals from a family as well as interrelation between various networks of a cutting edge multicultural world. The last option truth can prompt the unavoidable critical outcomes even to the evaporate of development due to an equipped struggle. This proof powers wide circles of logical social orders to create satisfactory implies for advancing the circumstance. In its illumination, it is no big surprise that the inclination of integration, of different fields science-based information become unmistakable highlights of the contemporary examinations. At present there are sensible justification for assuming that research of an unknown language scarcely, without providing some social mindfulness isn't to the point of accommodating common advantage in the global connections. This establishment fills in as a beginning stage for the beginning of a new science.

Thusly, the presence of linguoculturology is a proper aftereffect of creating of thoughtful and semantic hypothesis. At first the recommendation that there is a connection among's language and culture can be followed back to the perspectives on Humboldt. All in all the better we make colleague with the way of life of a country the more fruitful we ace the language. The most unmistakable regions recognized in Russia and in view of the interrelation of language and culture are as per the following: Linguo-country study. The examination in this space for the most part has an applied character and is an important wellspring of data, which mirrors the interrelation of language and culture. As indicated by the agents of social semantics (V. N. Teliya, V. V. Vorobyov, V. A. Maslova), this part of phonetics has as of late showed up "to the review and portrayal of the correspondence of language and culture in their synchronic collaboration". V. A. Maslova calls attention to the accompanying objects of social phonetics: 1) words and expressions, which have no counterparts in another language; 2) prime examples, ceremonies, convictions, and strange notions reflected in a language; 3) there are maxims and colloquialisms; 4) phrases; 5) images and generalizations; 6) similitudes and pictures; end the rundown expressive of standards and discourse conduct. Disregarding the way that the current situation with linguoculturology research is portrayed by an absence of general strategic establishments and normal calculated approaches; furthermore there is no clear hypothetical premise, regularly acknowledged wording, principal suspicions, which would permit delegates of various headings and patterns accomplish common arrangement. In addition, feelings vary with respect to

what ought to be viewed as linguoculturology and some examiners disregard the way that linguoculturology study is a free region with its own arrangement of ideas and a great history of academic examination; in any case linguoculturology has its own reasonable contraption and the "idea" which turns into the foundation of combination research. These days, mental desultory worldview has become customary, and with regards to its needs, the language has not currently considered as something that exists "in itself and for itself".^[2]

Today, the expression "idea" has acquired incredible notoriety in science, which is the crystallization of thought. The picture of idea is as two-sided solidarity of information, on the one handis confronting the language, the other is to the psychological universe of man. Thinking about the ideas "a lot of culture in human cognizance", the specialists N.D.Arutiunova, Y.S.Stepanov, A.D.Shmelev, E.S.Yakovlevshow thebasic conceptsthat existsin each andactual for each individual, be that as it may, they aren't just widespread, yet in addition are broadly explicit. Idea heart brilliant and adaptable addressed in expressiveness and is described by various signs. It is dynamic in nature and is firmly associated with the inward universe of man: to communicate feelings, state of mind, character, sentiments, for instance: /one's heart jumped in to one's mouth [throat]/душа в пяти ушло. The degree of connection of idea heart is in the piece of phraseological units in Uzbek and English permit to follow the acquainted molded of ideas, conceivable intermingling and disparity in the concentrated on languages and likewise in societies. A correlation of the lexical importance of the nominative units heart, filling in as semantically key word is permit to discuss fortuitous event of fundamental seme: heart: 1. the focal organ of the circulatory framework, as an empty strong sack that gives blood to the body; 2. organ, answerable for an individual's sentiments, his feelings, states of mind, sentiments, limit with regards to adore and empathy /one's heart warms towards her (him...), open one's heart to smb. Idea heart possesses a special spot in the perspective of Russian delegates of linguocultural local area. The heart is related to the character of the man, his life, it is morally important, exceptional idea, so it is famous thought of "open", "expansive", "secretive" heart, so it is enormous number of phraseological units with a part of the heart in the Uzbek and English languages. We said that the idea of heart is very much addressed in the phraseological asset of Uzbek what's more, English

² V.V. Vorobyev, Common and specific linguo country studies and Linguoculture Studies. Words and text in Dialogue, Moscow, 2000, P. 97.

languages.^[3] Manner, illustrations, axioms and truisms are a significant wellspring of data about the way of life of the attitude of individuals, they are mirrored the standpoint of the individuals straightforwardly or by implication. heart as the body answerable for the sensations of a man, his feelings, dispositions, sentiments, limit with regards to adore and compassion:with a large portion of a heart. heart is distress, hardship, flour:one's heart is breaking. heart is dread, sickness, nervousness: gobble up one's heart or on the other hand check this out; His heart was in his boots . heart is delight, fun: a light heart. heart is thoughtfulness, liberality, concern:one's heart warms towards her (him...). heart is the magnificence, compassion, love: from the botton of one's heart; lovely body an excellent soul. Close to one's heart; the spirit cheers.

As a rule, the idea heart opens up a wide field of examination, not just in the field of semantics, yet additionally brain research, human studies and ethnoculturology. The idea heart was assisted with moving toward the way of life and perspective of a group, who is to help the objective language, as address the appearance of a man inside.

Conclusion. It ought to be noticed that the Uzbek language word references offer from three to six word reference definitions heart, while English word references of more implications. Thus, notwithstanding fundamental implications, in English word references present a meaning of the word heart as a temperament or feeling, for instance: shift in perspective. In the two languages there is non-literal utilization of words, the elements improvement of implications. These days, there are following primary implications: the inward mystic universe of basic liberties, a man, the treatment. As you can find in the Uzbek, Russian and English languages, the essential implications are something very similar, yet there is a distinction in the semantic parts.

REFERENCES

1. E. Vereschagina, V.G. Kostamarov, Looking for new ways to develop linguo country studies: concept speech behavioral tactics. Moscow, 1999, pp. 84-86
2. V.A. Maslova, Linguoculturology, Academy Press, Moscow, 2001, P.115
3. V.V. Vorobyev, Common and specific linguo country studies and Linguoculture Studies. Words and text in Dialogue, Moscow, 2000, P. 97
4. G.L. Apperson, The Wordsworth Dictionary of Proverbs, Wordsworth Edition Ltd., 1993

³ G.L. Apperson, The Wordsworth Dictionary.of Proverbs, Wordsworth Edition Ltd., 1993

5. K. Sarekenova, The style comparison of Phraseology: Dissertation work, Almaty, 2001, pp. 20-26
6. V.V. Vorobiyev. Linguoculturology. (theory and practice): Monograph– М: 1997. - 113 p.
7. Umatova Zh.M., The concept of soul/жан as an linguocultural phenomena, Almaty, 30 (2005).